

Editorial

Algerian Journal of Chemical Engineering (AJCE)

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AJCE journal was created in order to cover the remarkable shortage of the Algerian journals, and so, provide a chance to the Algerian and worldwide researchers to publish their scientific works, after reviewing them through a carefully selected researches from decent university and institution over the world; we promise that our peer review process for every paper submitted to **AJCE** journal will be fast, reliable and looking forward the high quality of the succeed international worldwide journals. Moreover, we are committed to reply to all papers submitted in **AJCE** journal by six weeks with an acceptance or rejection answers.

In addition, the journal provides an experienced and knowledgeable editorial board and reviewers in different fields of Chemical Engineering, who give valuable constructive comments and remarks to authors for improving their papers and possible publications in **AJCE**.

The journal will achieve success through the commitment of its editorial board members, reviewers and the authors. Also, I hope through the high quality manuscripts published of **AJCE** journal, that we will provide the appropriate space for authors and motivate them to submit their work in **AJCE** journal.

Finally, I am grateful to all the editorial board members and reviewers in order to improve the quality of our journal.

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